

SOCIAL PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS IN THE PERFORMANCE OF THE TRADITIONAL SINGER OF THE XXI CENTURY

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Annotation: this article is currently providing feedback on social pedagogical conditions in the performance of traditional choral works in the 21st century. Detailed information is also described about the purpose tasks, pedagogical conditions, social status of the traditional singer.

Keywords: traditional singing, pedagogy, opportunities, music education and art, music performance, methodology.

The development of the higher education system in our country is determined by such urgent tasks as improving the quality of training of highly qualified personnel, demonstrating the mental abilities, talents of young people and creating conditions for formation as a physically and spiritually competent person. In the implementation of these urgent tasks, the “law on education” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state educational standards, the “national curriculum” of general secondary education are important documents.

One of the important problems facing the modern science of music pedagogy is the improvement of the effectiveness of the educational process. After all, music education is one of the important factors in ensuring spiritual maturation, and by influencing human feelings, it educates him spiritually-morally. In the following years, a number of regulatory and educational and methodological documents were adopted in the development of musical education in our country, programs were prepared, textbooks were published, educational and methodological literature was published.

There is a spiritual basis for our intention to educate a harmonious personality. Our first president was I.A.Karimov, grieving for the growing younger generation to become educated people in the future, states the following-“I want to say to our youth, to my children, that you never get tired of learning. Learning is never considered a fault. It is necessary to learn something if you do not know it. First of all, what is needed for young people who are now coming to life? It is necessary to learn, learn and once again learn. A person who has learned a profession, received knowledge, in Uzbek terms, will never be less.

Music education is one of the main and complex weapons of general education and teaches to highly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music not only Armes a person with high taste, but also forms spiritual worldviews.

Music is an important means of bringing students into the world of sophistication and moral and aesthetic education, with a strong focus on human emotions, the possibility of a strong influence. We can cite the words of our grandfather Sheikh Saadi "music is a satellite of the spirit of man". Music is an active developer of the emotional sensation that quickly affects a person. Therefore, the education of music culture, which is a component of human spirituality in students, remains the main goal of musical education.

Although the role of music in aesthetic education is sufficiently covered in the literature of philosophy, musicology and only the performer, but the role of traditional singing art in the spiritual and moral education of an individual has not yet received scientific coverage. This is due to the complexity of traditional singing art in our opinion and the versatility of its influence on the human mind. In this work, we will try to fill this defect, that is, to highlight the educational aspects of traditional singing and its role in maturing a new person and pedagogical conditions.

Goals and objectives of "traditional singing".

In Uzbek musical art, traditional singing has evolved and developed, adapting to different conditions depending on its field and direction. Among them are folklore sayings, epics, ritual sayings, modern academic(vocal) and variety singing, classical singing. Each direction has its own style, rules of law in terms of form and performance. Among them, the traditional Direction, formed within the framework of unchanging properties and reflecting the most perfect traditions, continues to be an example with all its character, potential. In the singer of classical music, the most beautiful traditions of the Uzbek people, their values associated with their national psyche arose, and the rich spirituality of the people was manifested. Therefore, in the tradition of singing, directions and styles of classical singing were formed. Doing this as traditional chivalric art directions has become urf. And the traditions of national classical singing developed into the basis of Uzbek traditional singing art.

"*Traditional chivalry*" consists in the formation of educational qualifications inherent in the art of chivalry, instilling in them the characteristics of being able to sing folk songs alone or, as a team, and of being able to organize status groups, with excellent knowledge of psychology and being able to lead a team. Based on the purpose of the science, a number of tasks are carried out in group classes.

- *To know the students who will be put in the leadership of the Makom singer and the Makamists' circle, and to go to him to learn.*

- *To learn about the nature of singing in a group and alone, didactic principles and other laws.*
- *To get acquainted directly with folk songs, songs and songs created by composers and samples of shashmakom and have a high artistic taste in their choice.*
- *In the process of singing in a team and working with a team, it is necessary to hiss the mental-physiological changes that occur in the human body and form skills for it.*

The traditional singing course carries out the following tasks: the study of traditional and folk singing. To give insight into 4 types of folk birds in traditional performance. Labor songs, season ritual and tradition songs, lyric songs, dials.

Another of the goals of the traditional singer is to prepare specialist personnel for the artistic communities of our Republic. Along with providing information about Uzbek folk songs as well as “Shashamaqom”, students are provided with information about the history of Creation, Performance range, voice use, dynamic characters, singer's performance status, measurements in works, methods, song Formation, performance techniques, information about the authors of the works under study and the necessary instructions. Science also serves to generate and teach the concepts and skills of Uzbek folk songs and cultivates in students feelings of love for traditional music as well as musical-artistic taste.

As a conclusion, we can say that the art of music is an important tool in the moral, cultural and educational upbringing of a person. Therefore, great attention has been paid to the art of music and its progress in all eras and society. Uzbek musical culture has an ancient and rich heritage. In its content, the life of the national psyche of our people is reflected in its higher human activities, artistic spirituality is the struggle for independence and independence, the hope of desire. The purpose of musical education education is to educate the younger generation, schoolchildren, adults at the level of a civilized person who can inherit our national musical heritage, perceive the wealth of Universal Music. To do this, students learn the art of music with all its sophistication, beauty, which requires its artistic perception, collective singing, dancing and extensive use in music culture training when they acquire the skills of creativity. The importance of traditional singing works in the upbringing of a perfect person is great. We must effectively use such performance works.

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